

Suggestions for faster implementation of risk-informed quality management

From the AAPM Working Group on TG-100 Implementation

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It's important to recognize that risk analysis is nothing new; you're already doing it. The tools recommended in the TG-100 report simply provide you with a structured way to approach it, thereby providing greater value for the effort you're expending.

By working together as a clinical team to map your processes, you're likely to discover opportunities for process efficiencies and simplification – so the effort is not purely additive to your workload.

Start small. It's OK to only focus on process mapping initially without any effort to perform FMEA or FTA if you are not making changes to your quality control or quality assurance. Simply discussing your process as a team will likely bring significant insight, clarity of the process and everyone's part in it, and awareness of potential risks.

For designing QC or QA for changes in your process, FMEA can simply be a listing of potential failure modes without ranking, since all risks need to be covered.

We recognize that resources available for risk analysis are often limited in busy radiotherapy clinics. Here, we have gathered a few select publications that describe efficient implementation of these techniques, with a focus on how teams can maximize the derived patient safety impact.

1. Brief tutorial videos on the core concepts in the TG-100 report:
<https://www.aapm.org/QualitySafety/TG100/ImplementationGuide.asp>
2. Virtual Library presentation from 2018 Annual Meeting on experiences with implementation: <https://aapm.org/education/VL/vl.asp?id=13064>
3. Schuller BW, Burns A, Ceilley EA, et al. Failure mode and effects analysis: A community practice perspective. *J Appl Clin Med Phys* 2017;18:258-267.
4. Ford EC, Smith K, Terezakis S, et al. A streamlined failure mode and effects analysis. *Med Phys* 2014;41:061709.
5. Paradis KC, Woch Naheedy K, Matuszak MM, et al. The fusion of incident learning and Failure Mode and Effects Analysis for data-driven patient safety improvements. *Pract Radiat Oncol* 2020;11:e106-e113.